

INFLUENCE OF CROSS-CULTURAL DIFFERENCES ON ACADEMIC PROCESS

Veronika Tarasova^{1*}, and Rozaliya Shakirzyanova²

¹Instructor of the Institute of International Relations, Kazan Federal University, RUSSIA,
edaminova@mail.ru

²Instructor of the Institute of International Relations, Kazan Federal University, RUSSIA,
rozalja_79@mail.ru

*Corresponding Author

Abstract

This study contributes to the existing problems of developing intercultural communication. Intercultural communication is a complex, phenomenon that includes various areas and forms of communication between individuals, groups and other communities. Interculturally oriented communication in the sense of globalization and science is very important for modern Russia. Today, more than ever, a foundation is needed for mutual understanding, an integral part of which is intercultural competence. Intercultural communication also involves the exchange and use of each other's experience, such as the generosity of the Russians, the wisdom of the Chinese, the hospitality of the Tatars, Kazakhs and Uzbeks. Here in Kazan Federal University we teach students from China, Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, North Africa and others. This experience helped us to detect the situations of cross-cultural misunderstanding. A list of knowledge, skills and qualities necessary for the recipient to ensure effective understanding of the speaker during oral intercultural communication is proposed. These skills, qualities and knowledge are components of the content of training aimed at removing difficulties in understanding foreign language spoken.

Keywords: intercultural communication; sociocultural structures; linguistic studies; scientific discourse; communicative barriers; inter-civilization dialogue

1. INTRODUCTION

Recent advances in information technology, an increased interest in expanding the relationships between different countries and peoples, are opening up new types and forms of communication the effectiveness of which is entirely dependent on mutual understanding of cultures, manifestations and respect for the culture of communicating partners. Intercultural communication competence provides the establishment, maintenance and development of its effective contacts with other people in various situations of interpersonal (including intercultural) communication and interaction. To teach students to use their creative potential, tolerate social, ethnic, confessional and cultural differences, to work in a team and conduct scientific researches is one of the most important components of training the modern and competitive person [1].

2. INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION TRAINING

Intercultural communication training promotes the formation of a person capable of mutual understanding, cooperation between peoples and cultures, educating students on the principles of humanism, tolerance, rapprochement of cultures of different countries, the development of a sense of unity and value of our civilization.

Professional communication is also impossible without knowledge of the cultural norms of the language being studied. Well-defined communication situations allow interaction between communicants on social topics and also from the field of professional interests of students.

The process of intercultural communication as well as of professional has their own laws that radically affect the interaction of the participants of communication. Based on this the aim of the article and the subject of our methodological research is the analysis of these types of communication.

Being not only a science, intercultural communication presents a set of skills that can and should be mastered. First of all, these skills are necessary for those whose activities are related to the interaction between cultures, who face obstacles of an inter-civilization nature when mistakes and communicative failures lead to ineffective results.

Different kinds of obstacles that arise in the process of intercultural communication are caused by different reasons, have different effects on the subjects of communication and, accordingly, have different consequences, insignificant on one hand and generating acute conflict situations on the other.

With the development of intercultural studies, new forms of training, called intercultural, or cross-cultural, appear. A new profession is emerging - a specialist in intercultural communication; an international society for intercultural education, training and research is being created." In this regard, the role of educational organization in which, at a certain stage of ontogenesis, the personality is socialized becomes extremely important. [2].

At present, intercultural communication in Russia has the status of an academic discipline, which relies on a developing network of research centres and higher educational institutions, and has a publishing base.

By intercultural communication, we understand the relationships that arise between individuals and groups belonging to different cultures. These relations always develop against the background of representations, codes defined by these cultures, a peculiar way of life.

Accordingly, intercultural communication training has become the most important area of modern university linguodidactics and is developing in strict accordance with modern social demand. The speed of global changes, the avalanche of events in the international arena, the unpredictability of their consequences for interstate relations are fully reflected in the nature and content-structural specifics of communication, with representatives of different cultures participating.

Not only the progression and personal success of the subject as a member of society, but also society as a whole, depend on the qualitative interaction of the individual with the environment, which is realized, first of all, in the process of communication.

Therefore, the role of the uncertainty factor in intercultural communicative space becomes dominant; under the uncertainty in this context, we mean "the parameter of the situation that the perceiving person cannot categorize, understand due to lack of information, overload-information or other reasons" [3]. The dominance of the uncertainty factor makes the problem of teaching a person to understand an interlocutor-foreigner extremely significant and the review of literature in linguodidactics shows that quite a lot of works have been devoted to its analyses and solution. (N.V. Elukhina, I.A. Zimnyaya, Z.I. Klychnikova, A.A. Leontiev, T.S. Serova, S.K. Folomkina, I.I. Khaleeva and others). This problem still continues to attract attention of researchers who, at the next round of the development of linguodidactic knowledge, comprehend the process of learning to understand a representative of another culture in a system of interculturally conditioned human relations. Real situations of intercultural interaction are sometimes ambiguous and complex. Not always communication partners receive satisfaction from communication with representatives of another culture. For successful contact and communication with representatives of different cultures, it is necessary to be aware of national differences, as well as to show respect and tolerance for national cultural characteristics.

Not less important is to form students' intercultural skills and ethnic tolerance: sensitivity to cultural

difference, respect for unique culture of other people, tolerance to an unusual mood and everything unexpected.

3. THE SURVEY

We conducted a short cross-cultural survey, the purpose of which was to find out how far the students are aware of national differences and intercultural misunderstanding. The subject of our study was students of years 2, 3 of the International Tourism Program.

There were 30 respondents to answer the following questions:

1. Have you ever had any communication problems with the representatives of other ethnic culture?
2. Where might cross-cultural misunderstanding take place?
 - a.) during academic process attending lectures or practical classes
 - b.). in public places: transport; cafeterias and restaurants; student's residence and/or dormitory
3. Have you ever had any communication problems with students from other countries in Kazan Federal University?
4. What problems do you encounter in cohabitation with students from other countries?

More than 75% of the survey participants never had any cultural misunderstanding situations. Cultural misunderstanding caused by misperception and misinterpretation might arise mostly in public places and not during classroom work: 68% of respondents proved it. While sharing rooms in student's residence 15 % of students have overcome some cultural difficulties. We have to notice that students experiencing cohabitation problems and difficulties speak neither Russian nor English fluently. This lack of clear understanding encourages students to continue learning English and Russian languages as a means of intercultural communication.

The subject's ability to recognize and overcome intercultural communication difficulties is considered as the basis for the development of intercultural competence. At the same time, we cannot overestimate the primary importance of language competence in the processes of intercultural communication. Language does not exist outside of culture, that is, outside of a socially inherited set of practical skills and ideas that characterize our lifestyle. "Language is in the centre of historical and social interaction in every society, in spite of location and time period." [4]

Thus, in the process of perceiving each other, representatives of different cultures often encounter difficulties and obstacles that interfere with their mutual understanding and can lead to conflict situations. The difficulties that usually arise are caused by cultural differences between partners, which cannot be levelled immediately in the communication process. Researchers define such difficulties in communication by the term "intercultural barriers".

In the scientific discourse devoted to various problems of intercultural communication, the terms "difficulties" and "barriers", which are often used as equivalent, are most often used to indicate causes that complicate and disrupt the communication process. However, in order to understand the causes of intercultural communication problems, it is necessary to distinguish between these concepts.

In the first case, the communication process only changes qualitatively, but does not break down and does not stop. To one degree or another, mutual understanding of partners is achieved. Therefore, in this case we can only talk about difficulties that do not create an impenetrable border between partners. For example, ignorance of the partner's language cannot serve as a reason for terminating communication, since it can be compensated by non-verbal and preverbal means. Therefore, these difficulties should be considered only as factors that reduce the quality of the communication process, but do not stop it.

To overcome these difficulties, the communicant must have special knowledge, skills and qualities necessary for successful understanding in the context of oral intercultural communication.

In contrast to difficulties, barriers in intercultural communication can be considered such factors that impede the interaction of partners and do not allow their mutual understanding. The reasons for communicative barriers can be the physiological defects of the participants (blindness, dumbness, deafness of one of them), belonging to different social groups, differences in cultural traditions, norms and values that determine the forms, methods and goals of communication [6].

Thus, intercultural communication, ensuring mutual understanding of the interlocutors, requires sufficient knowledge of the sociocultural background in the context of which the studied foreign language functions. Professional communication in the intercultural environment of specialists has a number of important characteristics. First and foremost, it is linguistic and cultural characteristics that make it possible to form linguistic competence; a foreign language can be considered not only as a means of communication and cognition, but also as a means of discovering the originality and uniqueness of a native culture. Awareness of the values of one's culture occurs only when one meets with representatives of other cultures and differences in their value orientations are revealed.

Linguistic phenomena reflect the facts of the social life of a given group of people. Culture-through-language studies are knowledge of vocabulary with national-cultural semantics and the ability to apply them in situations of intercultural communication.

The tasks of teaching a foreign language as a means of communication inextricably merge with the tasks of studying the social and cultural life of countries and peoples speaking this language. There is no doubt that culture is an integral part of human life and unable to exist independently of people. And at the same time, people are not free from the influence of culture, since people's behaviour is a function of culture [7]. Moreover, culture and communication are inseparable because culture not only dictates how the communication proceeds, it also helps to determine how people encode messages, the meanings they have for messages, and the conditions and circumstances under which various messages may or may not be sent, noticed, or interpreted [8].

Yet another effect that must be sought in the process of developing intercultural competence is acculturation, i.e. "The assimilation by a person who has grown up in one national culture of the essential facts, norms and values of another culture" [8].

Knowledge of cultural features is considered as the essential part of successful communication and this knowledge is thought to be highly important to solve some communicative tasks instilling self-development and self-realization skills in our students; to teaching them to use their creative potential, tolerate social, ethnic, confessional and cultural differences, to work in a team and to conduct scientific researches. [9], [10]. Cultural literacy means understanding discourse or culture: the ability to exercise communicating in the specific language of professionals (e.g., research in different fields of knowledge) [10].

Cultural background knowledge can be considered as the basis for the development of students' intercultural competence [11]. Each culture has its own norms and rules of behaviour, its own discursive style - the "manner of speech" (discourse) of native speakers of language culture, communication conventions that determine accepted and acceptable forms of expression of certain socially significant meanings. The ways of coding these meanings (not only linguistic ones), as well as the meanings themselves, can significantly differ in different cultures, which creates problems in intercultural communication, indicating that the systems of socially relevant values and ratings or systems of means do not coincide in the respective cultures.

Awareness of the values of one's culture occurs only when one meets with representatives of other cultures and differences in their value orientations are revealed.

Therefore, the assimilation of the science of dialogue contributes to the formation of a person's idea of himself as a citizen of the world, without giving up his national identity.

During the period of communication, the facts of the native culture are comprehended and reassessed; the student gets the opportunity to understand the possibility of a different interpretation of them. It is important that the fact of a different culture in the process of such an "intercultural" understanding begins to be interpreted as a natural "living" manifestation of the picture of the world of native speakers. Only in this case there is an opportunity for the formation of an intercultural personality, capable of mediating between two cultures as a result of a truly deep internal understanding of one's native and other culture.

To make the study of language and culture deeper and more productive, coordination with other humanitarian courses that are provided for studying in the direction of undergraduate training - world art culture, comparative linguistics, intercultural communications, history of Russia, history of Russian literature, the history of foreign literature will stimulate the progress [12].

4. CONCLUSIONS

Ending the article, we can draw the following conclusions:

1. The main way of teaching intercultural communication is the formation of intercultural competence by improving cultural education and developing tolerance.

2. The ability to compare native and foreign culture is a basic component of intercultural competence, and therefore the methods of its formation should be included in the model of teaching intercultural communication.

3. An effective method of teaching intercultural communication in the process of teaching foreign languages is an integrative-cultural study model based on a personality-activity approach and integrated training with subjects of the humanitarian and cultural studies cycle.

4. Dialogue of cultures stimulates creative development and spiritual enrichment of a person who comes into contact with the values of another culture.

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